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Improving Secondary School Students' Mathematics Problem Solving Skills Using Hypnotherapy Among Students with Mathematics Anxiety in Kebbi State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study was designed to determine the effect of hypnotherapy as veritable means of improving mathematics problem solving skills among Secondary School students with Mathematics anxiety in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Quasi experimental design was employed in the study and the target population was the entire senior secondary II students in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample of identified students that exhibited mathematics anxiety. Hypnotherapy package imbedded with deep relaxation and concentration strategy was deployed for the treatment of experimental group while conventional approach was used for control group with the aim of enhancing academic accomplishment in mathematics. After the therapy, Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) was administered to see the effect of the treatment in experimental group. The Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) was subjected to rigorous scrutiny to ensure its validity after which reliability was determine using split half method and then run Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) to obtain the reliability of the instrument. The index of 0.76 was obtained using Brown Prophecy Formula. The findings revealed that students exposed to hypnotherapy-based instruction performed significantly better in mathematics and demonstrated superior problem-solving skills compared to their counterparts who were taught with conventional approach. It was recommended among others that Schools should develop systems for the early identification of students suffering from mathematics anxiety. Once identified, these students can be provided with targeted interventions, including the hypnotherapy-based approach.

Keywords: Hypnotherapy, Mathematics anxiety, Problem solving skills, Academic performance, Mathematics

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics education transcends the mere acquisition of numerical proficiency; it encompasses holistic growth encompassing essential values such as rationality, control, and critical thinking. Mathematics anxiety, experienced by some students, can manifest as stress, aversion, dread, and even agony when confronted with mathematical problems (Mosahab, 2023). This condition impedes manipulating numbers and resolving mathematical problems in various contexts, from everyday life to academic scenarios (Salahod 2022). Its severity ranges from mild uneasiness to intense dread, leading to adverse reactions towards mathematical concepts and assessments. Mosahab (2023) stress that mathematics anxiety is closely associated with a “fear of performing mathematical tasks” and correlates with delayed comprehension of fundamental mathematical and numerical concepts, resulting in poor mathematical proficiency. Mathematics anxiety significantly impedes the ability to learn mathematics (Salahod 2022). Mathematics anxiety often develops due to prolonged stress experienced in mathematics classrooms, where time-constrained tests are frequently administered (Mosahab, 2023). It may also arise from competitive dynamics at home, such as with siblings or in the workplace. Mathematics anxiety substantially influences students’ mathematical thinking, affecting their reasoning and problem-solving abilities.

Hypnotherapy however, is a state of deep relaxation and focused concentration while learning. Hypnotherapy according to Lioffi, Kuttner, Wood & Zeltzer, (2013) is “a psychological state of heightened awareness and focused attention, in which critical faculties are reduced and susceptibility and receptiveness to ideas is greatly enhanced”. Through hypnotic interactions, Spiegel (2013) argued that students focused attention may be separated from negative thoughts leading to the reduction in anxiety which is associated with attentional control and ultimately leading to an improved concentration. Can info-graphic and hypnotherapy remediate dyslexia and improve performance in biology? The focus of this research

Mathematics is considered a difficult topic because of its abstract nature. The difficulty in learning mathematics is a global concern. It is an extremely significant and crucial subject in school education due to its relevance to everyday human life. As a result, it is taught as a core subject in schools around the world and is considered an important part of the school curriculum. Many students, particularly in mathematics and science, assume that success requires natural talent or even brilliance, rather than effort and sound techniques.

Problem Statement

Mathematics is been seen by many as a difficult subject and this difficulty is largely as a result of its abstract nature. The difficulty of learning mathematics seems to be a worldwide issue despite being it a necessary subject in school system as a result of its linkage to everyday human life. Students’ problem-solving skills is also found to be extremely below expectations. For student to study any science course, particularly engineering courses and other applied science related fields at tertiary institutions, it’s pertinent for one to have studied and passed mathematics at secondary school level. This made mathematics becoming central to future scientists globally. Despite this importance, the WAEC Chief examiner’s report 2024 indicated very poor results in mathematics specially areas where problem solving skills is required in mathematics. This scenario called for concern among parents, guidance, teachers and other stakeholders across the nation. If students with a normal learning condition could have issues with mathematics, it’s only interesting that students with mathematical anxiety should be giving a special attention because they have the chances of becoming future engineers and scientists that could break the world. Many students believe that it takes inherent ability or even brilliance to achieve well in mathematics, rather than the utilization of perseverance and good strategies. Mathematic anxiety is not a sickness and students with such issues can be the very best if handled with appropriate strategy.

It’s against this background that this study sought to find means of improving secondary school students’ mathematics problem solving skills using hypnotherapy among students with mathematics anxiety in Kebbi state, Nigeria. Thus, this research is potentially significant to secondary school students with mathematics anxiety as well as all other stakeholders in educational sector in Nigeria, hence justifying the need for the research

Literature Review

Hypnotherapy

Hypnotherapy according to Imelda et al., (2019) is defined as a state of consciousness involving focused attention and reduced peripheral awareness characterized by an enhanced capacity for responding to suggestions (Elkins et al., 2019). Moreover, most studies defined hypnotherapy as an induced state characterized by increased suggestibility in which learners are susceptible to suggestions that change perceptions, feelings, thoughts, and behavior by concentrating on ideas and images uttered by the therapist (Heap, 2015)

Hypnosis consists of cognitive and behavioral elements that can help alleviate learning difficulties. The cognitive element involves visualization and imagination, while the relaxation component is a behavioral element that can be used to reduce learning difficulties including test anxiety. Hence, by providing suggestions, ego-strengthening, and relaxation or progressive relaxation during hypnosis, students can be assisted in managing and improving their performance (Zahedi, & Sommer, 2022). Along with other well-known creative modalities of expression like painting and poetry, “being hypnotic” can also be considered as a creative mode of expression and communication. Hypnosis involves a relative suspension of conscious awareness which is generally induced through suggestions of progressive relaxation that in turn stimulates a state of concentration and focused attention. According to Zahedi, & Sommer, (2022) hypnotherapy has very effectively been used to treat a variety of learning difficulties as well as physical and psychological ailments. With the use of hypnotherapy on students who have low learning motivation, it is expected that learning motivation will increase. This statement is supported by research (Imelda et al., 2019).

According Kai & Yu (2021), the process of hypnotherapy can be divided into pre-suggestion, suggestion, and post-suggestion phases. The pre-suggestion component may include selective attentional focusing with distraction, imagery, and relaxation methods. The aim is to reach an altered state of consciousness in which the conscious mind is relaxed, the unconscious mind is more accessible, and the subject is susceptible to suggestion. In the suggestion phase, specific goals or impressions are presented, questions may be asked of the subject, or memories may be explored. The post-suggestion phase occurs after a return to a normal state of consciousness, and new behaviors based on hypnotic suggestions may be practiced. It has been suggested that there is a risk of false memories (confabulation) as a result of some types of hypnotherapy, although scientific research is limited in this area.

Mathematics anxiety

Learning anxiety has been defined as a situation specific anxiety trait (Sapp, 2009). When exposed to evaluative situations individuals can react with tension, excessive worry and mental disorganization among other symptoms (Sarason, 2012). Correlational investigations have shown that compared to subjects with low scores, subjects with high scores on measures of exam anxiety tend to perform relatively poorly on various types of ability tests (Sapp, 2009). However, Sarason (2012) noted that studies have suggested that highly anxious people are not academically less able. The concern therefore is that reactions to evaluative situations could lead to underperformance in examination situations; in other words students who have the ability to achieve well academically may perform poorly because of the effects of anxiety. Mathematics anxiety appears to be a relatively widespread problem (Spielberger, 2022) and finding ways to reduce its effects has become increasingly important. One possible intervention which has been suggested as a treatment for exam anxiety is hypnosis (Sapp, 2009). Hypnosis has been used to treat a number of anxiety disorders including post-traumatic stress disorder (Sarason, 2012).

There are two major features of hypnosis: the first is a cognitive component, and the second is a relaxation component (Sapp, 2009). As Sapp noted (2009) it is a combination of these two components that may make hypnosis effective in reducing exam anxiety. Relaxation procedures may reduce exam related increases in self-reported distress symptoms, and relaxation procedures have also been associated with immunologic changes in other investigations. Research to date suggests promising results of hypnotherapy in the treatment of learning and examination anxieties. A recent systematic review and

meta-analysis conducted by (Spielberger, 2022) concluded that hypnotherapy is effective in reducing examination anxiety (effect size -0.39 95%CI -0.662 to -0.005).

Problem solving skills in mathematics

In recent years, educational studies have tended to focus on how to teach and develop thinking, which is one of the most essential tasks of the teacher in today's teaching approaches (Joshi & Sheela, 2020). Whereas the focus on problem-solving ability has become an issue worthy of investigation, students of various educational levels attain it to be able to handle practical obstacles, whether academic or life-related (Rajkumar & Nachimuthu, 2019). Because problem-solving abilities are at the top of the learning pyramid, they are extremely important in the lives of students (Pathak, 2015). As thinking strategies enable pupils to regulate their own thinking processes, it acts as the information processing model on the consideration of the individual executing his action in light of the information he gets (Rajkumar & Nachimuthu, 2019). The problem solving strategy was associated with the American scientist who laid the groundwork for its use in his book "How do we think and how do we solve problems?" The problem was defined as a perplexing situation that raises doubt and uncertainty in the educated individual (Malkawi, Alhadrami & Aljabri, 2019). Kantowski (2022) described problem-solving as a process consisting of a set of behaviors, actions, or activities that guide an individual to a solution. Krulik and Rudnick (2022) described problem-solving as a process consisting of a series of behaviors, actions, or activities that guide an individual to a solution.

The ultimate objective of educational institutions across the world is to create positive students who can use all of their intellectual talents to solve challenges in new scenarios (Malkawi et al., 2019). This requirement arose from the realization of students' failure to identify acceptable answers in new settings, and later the inability of academic graduates, especially professionals accountable for attaining societal growth and development (Bala & Shaafiu, 2016). This is because students' challenges are caused not largely by a lack of scientific understanding, but by the application of unsuitable problem-solving strategies (Joshi & Sheela, 2020). Previous research (i.e. Pathak, 2015, Rajkumar & Nachimuthu, 2019, Malkawi et al., 2019, Joshi & Sheela, 2020) on students at various levels revealed that they were unable to answer the challenges provided to them, although possessing the necessary information. The lack of identification and comprehension of the concerns was discovered after examining the pupils' responses. Driver and Bell (2023) stated that studying science necessitates the capacity to process, evaluate, and construct prior knowledge in order to provide meaning to what pupils experience or identify what they observed.

However, in recent years, academics have shifted their focus to the reasons of mathematical learning challenges, as well as the learner's procedural on problem solving skills particularly mathematics. Mathematics is viewed as the result of human activities in the process of adapting to the outside world. The exact acquisition of mathematical abilities requires a wide range of general cognitive capabilities, including mathematics problem solving skills (Kunwar, Shrestha, & Sharma, 2021). These skills enable students to engage in a variety of mathematical activities and performances. Working memory is a powerful predictor of mathematical skills over time, achievement, and growth in mathematics (Kunwar, Shrestha, and Sharma, 2021).

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was stated as follows;

- a. Find out if there is any difference in the academic performance of students with mathematics anxiety when taught mathematics using hypnotherapy-based strategy and conventional approach in Kebbi state, Nigeria
- b. Find out if the problem-solving skills of students with mathematics anxiety will improve if taught mathematics using hypnotherapy-based strategy and conventional approach in Kebbi state
- c. Find out if there is any difference in the academic performance of male and female students with mathematics anxiety when taught mathematics using hypnotherapy-based strategy in Kebbi state

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- a. What is the difference in the academic performance of students with mathematics anxiety when taught mathematics using hypnotherapy-based strategy and conventional approach in Kebbi state, Nigeria?
- b. Does the problem-solving skills of students with mathematics anxiety improve if taught mathematics using hypnotherapy-based strategy and conventional approach in Kebbi state?
- c. Is any difference in the academic performance of male and female students with mathematics anxiety when taught mathematics using hypnotherapy-based strategy in Kebbi state?

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students with mathematics anxiety taught using a hypnotherapy-based strategy and those taught using the conventional approach in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the problem-solving skills of students with mathematics anxiety taught using a hypnotherapy-based strategy and those taught using the conventional approach in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students with mathematics anxiety taught using a hypnotherapy-based strategy in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Design: The study employed quasi experimental design approach, which will involve pretest and posttest approach. The design will allow the manipulation of one or more variables (referred to as the independent variable), followed by the observation of the resulting effects on the dependent variable. To evaluate their impact on the target group, the researchers use hypnotherapy-based instructional strategy. The study involved the division of participants into two unique groups which are experimental group and control group with an identified students with mathematics anxiety. The experimental group will be made up of identified students with difficult mathematics problem solving skills that will be treated with hypnotherapy based instructional strategy while control group will constitute identified students with difficult mathematics problem solving skills that will be treated with conventional approach. Algebra will be used as the mathematical topic for the study. This is because algebra is central to mathematics and require some level of identification of numbers.

Population, sample and sampling technique: Population of the study comprised of the entire senior secondary II students in Kebbi state with a total number of 3,987. Sample of 97 students was drawn from the population using purposive sampling techniques. This is necessary because the research involve identified unique set of students with difficult mathematics problem solving skills. According to Matazu 2021, in quasi experimental research, minimum of 10 sample is enough for the study. The population of this study are most Hausa speaking students, with substantial number of Dakarkari, Arewawa and Kambari while some small percentages are Yoruba, Igbo and other minority from across the country. A conscious effort was made to include representative groups of students from across the six educational zones of the state.

Research Instrument, validation and reliability

The utilization of hypnotherapy package imbedded hypnosis-based strategy was deployed for the treatment of experimental group while conventional approach was used for control group with the aim of enhancing academic accomplishment. After the therapy, Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) was administered to see the effect of the treatment in both experimental and control groups. The Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) underwent rigorous scrutiny to ensure its validity after which reliability was also be determine using split half method and then running Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) which gave the reliability of the either half. After, the index gotten was also be subjected to Brown Prophecy Formula in order to get the reliability of the full instrument and the reliability index of 0.76 was obtained. This study used 2024/2025 academic year. Data generated was analyzed using descriptive statistics and T-test

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Research Question 1: *What is the difference in the academic performance of students with mathematics anxiety when taught mathematics using hypnotherapy-based strategy and conventional approach in Kebbi state, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
Experimental Group (Hypnotherapy)	52	68.45	8.12
Control Group (Conventional)	45	60.20	7.75

Table 1 depict that the experimental group had a higher mean score (M = 68.45, SD = 8.12) than the control group (M = 60.20, SD = 7.75). This suggests that the hypnotherapy-based instructional strategy significantly improved the mathematics performance of students with mathematics anxiety.

Ho: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students with mathematics anxiety taught using a hypnotherapy-based strategy and those taught using the conventional approach in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Table 2: T-test for the Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Mean	Sta. Dev.	df	t-cal	p-value
Experimental Group (Hypnotherapy)	52	68.45	8.12	95	5.01	0.001
Control Group (Conventional)	45	60.20	7.75			

The result in table 2 revealed a statistically significant difference in the academic performance of students in the experimental group who were taught using hypnotherapy-based strategy compared to those in the control group who received conventional instruction, $t(95) = 5.01, p < 0.001$.

Research Question 2: *Does the problem-solving skills of students with mathematics anxiety improve if taught mathematics using hypnotherapy-based strategy and conventional approach in Kebbi state?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Problem-solving Skill for Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Mean Problem-Solving Score	Standard Deviation
Experimental Group	52	70.65	7.48
Control Group	45	62.90	6.85

Table 3 showed that students in the experimental group (M = 70.65, SD = 7.48) outperformed those in the control group (M = 62.90, SD = 6.85), indicating that the hypnotherapy-based strategy effectively enhanced their problem-solving skills.

Table 4: T-test for the Problem-Solving Skill of Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	df	t-cal	p-value
Experimental Group	52	70.65	7.48	95	5.54	0.001
Control Group	45	62.90	6.85			

The result in table 4 indicated that there is a significant difference in mathematics problem-solving skills between students taught using hypnotherapy and those taught using the conventional method, $t(95) = 5.54, p < 0.001$.

Research Question 3: *Is any difference in the academic performance of male and female students with mathematics anxiety when taught mathematics using hypnotherapy-based strategy in Kebbi State?*

Table 5: Mean and standard Deviation on Gender in the Experimental Group

Gender	N	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
Male	28	69.75	7.88
Female	24	67.05	8.40

Table 5 showed that males had a slightly higher mean score ($M = 69.75$, $SD = 7.88$) compared to females ($M = 67.05$, $SD = 8.40$), this difference was not significant.

Table 6: T-test on Gender difference in the Experimental Group

Gender	N	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	df	t-cal	p-value
Male	28	69.75	7.88	50	1.27	0.21
Female	24	67.05	8.40			

The outcome in table 6 revealed no statistically significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students taught using hypnotherapy-based strategy, $t(50) = 1.27$, $p = 0.21$.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated the effectiveness of a hypnotherapy-based instructional strategy in improving the academic performance and problem-solving skills of secondary school students with mathematics anxiety in Kebbi State, Nigeria. The findings revealed a statistically significant difference in academic performance between the experimental and control groups. This suggests that students who received instruction through the hypnotherapy-based strategy performed significantly better in mathematics than their counterparts who were taught with the conventional approach. The rejection of the null hypothesis indicates that the intervention was effective in mitigating the negative effects of mathematics anxiety and enhancing academic outcomes. This finding supports previous studies by Spielberger, (2022) that highlight the benefits of alternative therapeutic methods, such as hypnotherapy, in addressing emotional barriers to learning and improving cognitive function and academic engagement which is furthermore in agreement with the findings of Kai & Yu (2021). The analysis also revealed a significant difference in problem-solving skills between the experimental and control groups, which implies that the hypnotherapy-based strategy not only improved general academic performance but also enhanced higher-order thinking and analytical skills in mathematics. The rejection of H_02 confirms that the intervention had a substantial positive impact on students' ability to approach and solve mathematical problems effectively. This finding aligns with that of Joshi & Sheela, (2020), Kantowski, (2022) who agreed that hypnotherapy can enhance mental clarity, reduce performance anxiety, and promote strategic thinking, the findings also align with the study conducted by Rajkumar, & Nachimuthu, (2019). In contrast to the previous hypotheses, the third hypothesis was not rejected as the result indicated no statistically significant difference between male and female students in the experimental group, although males had slightly higher mean scores than females, the difference was not statistically meaningful. This suggests that the hypnotherapy-based instructional strategy was equally effective for both genders, same as the view of Salahot, (2022). The outcome indicates that the benefits of hypnotherapy in reducing anxiety and enhancing mathematics performance are not gender-biased, and that both male and female students responded similarly to the intervention. The consistent pattern of improved performance and problem-solving skills among students taught using the hypnotherapy-based strategy suggests that this method is a viable complementary approach to traditional mathematics instruction, especially for students with anxiety-related learning difficulties. The strategy appeared to foster a more relaxed learning environment, increase mental focus, and boost students' confidence and resilience when facing mathematical tasks. These findings highlight the potential for integrating hypnotherapy-based practices into secondary school

teaching, particularly within remedial or inclusive education settings. The gender-neutral effect further supports the adaptability and universal benefit of the intervention.

CONCLUSION

This study was carried out to examine the effectiveness of a hypnotherapy-based instructional strategy in improving academic performance and problem-solving skills among secondary school students with mathematics anxiety in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Using a quasi-experimental design involving an experimental group and a control group, the study provided evidence-based insights into how therapeutic interventions such as hypnotherapy can play a transformative role in mathematics education. The findings revealed that students exposed to hypnotherapy-based instruction performed significantly better in mathematics and demonstrated superior problem-solving skills compared to their counterparts who were taught with conventional approach. The results also indicated that the intervention was effective for both male and female students, as there was no significant gender difference in performance within the experimental group. Conclusively, the study affirms that hypnotherapy is a promising and effective tool for improving mathematics learning outcomes among students with mathematics anxiety. It calls for the consideration of innovative and holistic teaching approaches that cater not only to intellectual needs but also to emotional and psychological well-being.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made to enhance mathematics teaching and address mathematics anxiety among secondary school students in Kebbi State and beyond:

1. Education stakeholders, particularly school administrators and curriculum planners, should consider incorporating hypnotherapy-based strategies into mathematics instruction, especially for students identified with high levels of mathematics anxiety. This can be done through teacher training or collaboration with qualified mental health professionals.
2. Teachers and school counselors should be trained in basic therapeutic and mindfulness techniques, including elements of hypnotherapy, to support students' emotional well-being and improve their engagement in subjects perceived as difficult, such as mathematics.
3. Schools should develop systems for the early identification of students suffering from mathematics anxiety. Once identified, these students can be provided with targeted interventions, including the hypnotherapy-based approach.
4. Since the study found no significant gender difference in the effectiveness of the hypnotherapy-based strategy, schools should adopt this method inclusively without gender bias, ensuring that both male and female students benefit equally from the intervention.
5. This study should be replicated in other educational zones and with larger sample sizes to further validate the effectiveness of hypnotherapy in educational settings.

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